

PRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF EUPHEMISMS IN POLITICAL MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda ommaviy axborot vositalari nutqiga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqotdagi eng so'nggi topilmalar Evfemizmlarning hissiy va baholangan malakasi ifodalangan. Gazeta maqolasidagi evfemizmlar ommaviy axborot vositalarining nutqi darajasida namoyon bo'ladi. Maqolada evfemizmlarning semantik, strukturaviy va pragmatik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Evfemizmlar, o'ziga xosliklar, semantik va pragmatik xususiyatlar, lingva-madaniy yondashuv

Аннотация: В настоящее время медиадискурсу уделяется особое внимание. Самые последние выводы в этом исследовании выражают эмоционально-оценочную квалификацию эвфемизмов. Эвфемизмы в газетной статье проявляются на уровне медийного дискурса. В статье рассматриваются семантические, структурные и прагматические характеристики эвфемизмов.

Ключевые слова: эвфемизмы, особенности, семантические и прагматические признаки, лингвокультурологический подход.

Abstract: Nowadays, media discourse receives special emphasis. The most recent findings in this study Euphemisms' emotional and assessed qualification is expressed. Euphemisms in newspaper article manifest themselves on the level of media discourse. The article examines the semantic, structural, and pragmatic characteristics of euphemisms.

Key words: Euphemisms, peculiarities, semantic and pragmatic features, lingua-cultural approach

A word has enormous power and may elicit a variety of responses. As a result, language users aim to avoid employing nasty, unpleasant, uncomfortable, or overly direct language. An euphemism is a replacement of a statement by a sender with one that may be unpleasant or damaging to the receiver speech that is less hurtful or disturbing.

The many phases of social psychology are reflected in euphemism. Many societal factors Euphemism may be explained by psychology. Avoiding taboos, being polite. The most fundamental and common is to disguise one's speech. The main goal is to avoid taboos. Euphemisms are produced on a psychological foundation. The names of gods and goddesses are used in numerous cultures.

Devils are forbidden, and people strive to avoid directly referencing them. That is why the English rename "Satan" as "god of this earth," "his sable majesty," or "old gentleman in the sky."

Language is a system of characters that came into being from men's common labour, being developed and enriched in the course of time. With the development of our society, a fair number of words are labelled frivolous, vulgar or at least inconsiderate, and some kinds of languages are forbidden, as different religions, superstitious beliefs, social customs and other reasons.

In communication, for better maintaining social relationship and exchanging ideas, people have to resort to a new different kind of language, which can make distasteful ideas seem acceptable or even desirable (www.docstoc.com).

Euphemisms are terms that we employ to soften the harsh reality that surrounds us. They are euphemisms. Languages have universal features; practically all societies use them to talk about topics that are universal.

Euphemisms are frequently seen in colloquial terms known to native speakers. Speakers of one culture who are not easily understood by speakers of another. Euphemisms may be employed out of genuine concern for not offending someone's feelings. Some lexical items in the newspaper text can be grouped as a euphemistic substitute.

Words with usually positive meanings are useful for euphemistic renomination because decoding the positive connotations of the offered phrases are actualized, allowing for the smoothing of the most unfavorable correlations. A euphemism is a phrase that appears in a standard newspaper denotes a certain level of manifestation of the attribute. Such expressions are interpreted negatively.

We use euphemisms in different spheres of life without considering which euphemism to use and when, however, it is not so easy to classify them as there is no uniform standard. Euphemisms can be classified according to different criteria, rules, or principles. The following is a presentation of some possible classifications of euphemisms.

Rawson divides euphemisms into two general types, namely, positive and negative which are distinguished according to the evaluative aspect (1981). (Laura Samoskaite 2011: 11)

Researchers are attempting to include socio-cultural factors into modern linguistic speech. The euphemism's linguistic and pragmatic aspects. The definition, in our opinion, should reflect contextual reliance and pragmatic focus are crucial characteristics of euphemism. We feel that euphemism is a figure of speech that is utilized instead of the direct candidate stigmatic.

Euphemisms are commonly used to avoid saying something hurtful or unpleasant. Euphemisms are widely used while discussing violence, ability, or any other topic that is relevant.

It is seen as taboo or unacceptable in society. According to various standards euphemisms. We have discovered that some euphemisms have an exact counterpart in both languages. Euphemisms allow us to express ourselves in a pleasant manner without offending others.

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